

Web Scraper Application for E-commerce Website

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ABSTRACT

In the rapidly evolving digital world, efficient extraction of data from the web is essential for insights and decision-making. This tool introduces a versatile web scraping solution by making use of Puppeteer. Puppeteer excels in dynamic web page interactions. The use of this libraries capabilities forms a robust approach for navigating and scraping modern websites. The resulting tool enables seamless extraction of both static and dynamic content, providing researchers, analysts, and businesses with a powerful tool to acquire structured data from diverse web sources, facilitating data-driven decisions and research across multiple domains. The power of this library offers an end to end solution for automating data extraction. It also emphasizes on ethical considerations and the importance of adhering to legal and site-specific scraping policies ensuring responsible data extraction practices. Web scraper tool can give a huge advantage to businesses in today's market where data-driven decision-making is of high importance. By leveraging this tool, our solution enhances the efficiency, accuracy of web scraping tasks. We explore various aspects of the scraping process, including handling dynamic content, authentication mechanisms, and data extraction techniques. Furthermore, we address challenges related to website structure changes and anti-scraping mechanisms, creating effective strategies to overcome these obstacles and make data extraction easy and efficient.

Keywords: Web Scraper, Puppeteer, E-commerce Product Tracking, Affordable Price Notifications.

I. INTRODUCTION

This tool utilizes Puppeteer to develop an efficient web scraping solution for e-commerce websites. It focuses on extracting product details, pricing information, from dynamic online marketplaces. The primary goal is to create a versatile and scalable scraping tool that can overcome challenges like CAPTCHA and dynamic loading. By using Puppeteer for simulating user interactions, the web app aims to provide practical data extraction techniques. The resulting data can empower businesses, researchers, and developers with real-time e-commerce insights, aiding in informed decision-making and digital strategy enhancement. E-commerce has become a dominant force in the retail sector, and its rapid growth is driven by data-driven decision-making. In an intensely competitive market, access to real-time, accurate, and comprehensive data is vital for businesses. Web scraper is motivated by the need to empower common people with the ability to track product prices and buy them when prices are affordable. This can be done by scraping essential information such as product availability, pricing from online marketplaces. Through this web scraping application, we aim to provide the means for users to better understand their market, optimize pricing strategies, and respond dynamically to customer preferences, ultimately enhancing their profitability and market presence. The motivation for this web app also comes from the limitations imposed by e-commerce websites that frequently change and employ dynamic loading techniques and CAPTCHA challenges. By adopting Puppeteer, we aim to overcome such hurdles and develop a resilient web scraping solution. Having the ability to gather data from e-commerce websites opens avenues for market analysis, trend identification, and consumer behavior research. This web scraper tool strives to provide a valuable resource for researchers, offering the tools and strategies to access and analyze the wealth of information present on e-commerce platforms. In doing so, it supports evidence-based decision-making and drives innovation within the e-commerce industry.

II. LITERATURE WORK

We have explored a wide range of research papers that have given us idea about different web scraping approaches

Paper titled 'Web Scraping Approaches and their Performance on Modern Websites' by Ajay Sudhir Bale highlights the evolving landscape of web scraping and its implications for data acquisition in the digital age. Using technologies like crawler bot, dom parsing, headless browser, efficient web scraping can be done.

Paper titled 'Web Scraping based Product Comparison Model for E-Commerce Websites' by Harsh Khatter introduces a novel and efficient product comparison model that leverages web scraping to enhance the E-commerce shopping experience for users. Paper describes different tools like Selenium, Beautiful soup using which E-commerce product data can be scraped.

Paper titled 'Comparative Study of Various Scraping Tools: Pros and Cons' by Priya Matta explains about various web scraping tools such as puppeteer, superagent, scrapy. Each has its own benefits and limitations the choice of the tools to use depends on the requirements of the task.

Paper titled 'Co-Mart A Daily Necessity Price Comparison Application' by Ayush Asawa explains a system that is used to collect and store data of products that are used in daily life. The prices of these products are compared and tracked to maximize profit by buying daily necessity products at discounted prices.

A study by Glez-Peña et al. (2014) discusses the implementation of web scraping using DOM parsing, regular expressions, and XPath queries, highlighting the effectiveness of these methods in extracting structured data from complex web pages. Additionally, machine learning algorithms have been increasingly applied to identify and extract relevant information from web pages. For instance, the use of Natural Language Processing (NLP) and computer vision techniques to analyze and scrape data from semi-structured and unstructured content is discussed by Ferrara et al. (2014).

An empirical study by Kang et al. (2016) shows how web scraping can be used to collect pricing data from multiple e-commerce websites to build a comprehensive price comparison tool. This application helps consumers find the best deals and enables businesses to adjust their pricing strategies in real-time.

According to Jadhav and Channe (2016), scraping reviews and ratings from e-commerce sites like Amazon and eBay allows businesses to understand consumer sentiments and preferences, which is crucial for market analysis and decision-making. The authors demonstrate how sentiment analysis on scraped review data can reveal trends and insights about product popularity and consumer satisfaction.

Technical challenges in web scraping include dealing with dynamic content, anti-scraping mechanisms, and data quality issues. Websites increasingly use JavaScript to load content dynamically, which complicates the scraping process. Mitigating these challenges often requires sophisticated tools like Selenium or headless browsers. Anti-scraping mechanisms, such as CAPTCHAs and IP blocking, necessitate the development of strategies to bypass these defenses, as discussed by Sakhare et al. (2017). Ensuring the accuracy and completeness of the scraped data is also a critical concern.

Web scraping is also utilized for inventory management. Researchers like Wu et al. (2015) have explored how scraping data about product availability and stock levels can help businesses maintain optimal inventory and prevent stockouts or overstocking. This application is particularly beneficial for businesses operating in highly competitive and dynamic markets.

All of the above knowledge was helpful for building our web scraper application for E-commerce website. We used collected information to build a complete application.

III. METHODOLOGY

We have used a web scraping library called Puppeteer for extracting product data from e-commerce website like flipkart. Puppeteer is also called as a headless browser. This library can be used to interact with a website in way that feels like an actual human being is doing it. This web app also has a feature of setting an affordable price for e-commerce products. When the price of product decreases below a certain price, an email is sent to the user informing about the decreased price, this tells user that, now the product is in affordable range and user can buy it. To send email we have used a javascript library called nodemailer. The user can create account using an email and a password. The password is hashed and stored securely in the database. For creating frontend HTML5, CSS3, JavaScript are used and for backend Nodejs, MongoDB are used.

A. Working of Signup and Login System.

Users can create an account from signup page using an email and a password. This data is then stored in the database, password is first hashed using a library called bcryptjs and then stored in the database. When a user tries to log in from login page, if the username and password are correct then user is redirected to home page otherwise appropriate message is displayed on the screen.

B. How to Search Products ?

When user logs in, home page is displayed. Using search bar on the home page user can search for products. The searched product is sent to the backend and here program uses puppeteer to go to Flipkart website and extract product name and price, then this data is displayed on the home page.

C. How to set Affordable Price for Product Tracking ?

When user clicks on any product displayed on the home page, user is redirected to another page which displays the product information and input box for setting an affordable price for the product. If the price of this product decreases below affordable price then user is notified by an email, informing the user that now the product is in affordable range and that the user can buy it.

D. Saved Products Functionality.

The products that user is tracking can be seen on the saved products page. On this page user can change the affordable price based on requirement. The user can also remove products to stop tracking the product prices.

E. Contact Functionality.

The users can contact the website support team using contact page. Here user can just enter fields like name, email and message. An email is then sent to the website support team. User can ask about any question they might have about the web scraper application.

F. Personalized Dashboard for Users.

An account page is available on the website. Using the account page users can logout, delete account etc. if the account is deleted then all the data related to a user account is deleted from the database.

G. Libraries Used for the Backend Functionality.

Puppeteer is the main library used for web scraping. Expressjs, bcryptjs, nodemailer are some of the libraries that are used for tasks like creating a server, hashing data, sending emails etc.

Drawbacks:

1. Website Structure Changes

E-commerce websites frequently update their structures, making it challenging to maintain consistent scraping functionality. Changes in HTML/CSS elements can break existing scraping scripts, necessitating constant monitoring and adjustments.

2. Robots.txt and Legal Constraints

Some websites may explicitly disallow web scraping in their robots.txt files. While the web scraper respects these rules, adherence to website terms of use and legal regulations is essential. Violations could result in legal repercussions.

3. CAPTCHA Challenges

CAPTCHA challenges can hinder automated scraping. While the web scraper aims to bypass CAPTCHA, it may not always be successful, leading to interrupted scraping or requiring manual intervention.

4. Dynamic Loading

Websites that use dynamic loading techniques may pose challenges. The web scraper can handle some forms of dynamic content, but complex or highly customized loading mechanisms may be difficult to navigate.

Architecture Diagram:

Figure 1: Architecture Diagram of Web Scraper Application

IV. RESULTS

Figure 2: Home Page of Web Scraper Application

Figure 3: Saved Products Page of Web Scraper Application

Figure 4: Contact Page of Web Scraper Application

Figure 5: Account Page of Web Scraper Application

The screenshot shows the Myscraper login page. At the top, there is a blue octopus logo followed by the text "MYSCRAPER". Below the logo, there are two input fields: "Email" and "Password". Underneath these fields is a blue button labeled "Login". At the bottom of the page, there is a link that says "Don't have an account ? [Create an Account](#)" and a link that says "Forgot password?".

Figure 6: Login page of Web Scraper Application

The screenshot shows the Myscraper signup page. At the top, there is a blue octopus logo followed by the text "MYSCRAPER". Below the logo, there are three input fields: "Email", "Password", and "Confirm Password". Underneath these fields is a blue button labeled "Create Account". At the bottom of the page, there is a link that says "Already have an account ?" followed by a link labeled "[Log In](#)".

Figure 7: Signup page of Web Scraper Application

V. CONCLUSION

The web scraping tool built using Puppeteer for e-commerce websites presents a powerful solution for accessing real-time data in the digital marketplace. Throughout this endeavor, we have addressed the core challenges associated with data extraction, adaptability to dynamic content, and overcoming hurdles like CAPTCHA challenges. This tool has equipped common users, businesses, researchers, and analysts with the tools and strategies to unlock valuable insights, strategic decisions, and track market trends. In conclusion, the advantages of this web scraper are numerous. It offers the ability to gain a competitive edge through real-time data access and competitive intelligence, facilitating data-driven decision-making. The web app's automation and user-friendly interface enhance its utility, ensuring that users can configure, schedule, and analyze scraped data efficiently. Furthermore, the system prioritizes security, compliance, and responsible use, addressing ethical and legal considerations in web scraping.

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